

THE DETERMINATION OF THE PARACHORS OF INORGANIC SALTS IN SOLUTIONS AND THEIR STRUCTURE. PART II. SOME LITHIUM, SODIUM, RUBIDIUM SALTS AND ATOMIC PARACHORS OF THE ABOVE ELEMENTS INCLUDING CAESIUM.

BY JAMIAT V. LAKHANI AND RUSTOM P. DAROGA.

The parachors of some lithium, sodium and rubidium salts have been determined by the solution method and the parachor values of lithium bromide, sodium thiosulphate and sodium bisulphite which have not been previously determined are now found by this method.

For the first group of elements (Li, Na, K, Rb, Cs) the graph obtained by plotting the log of atomic number against the log of parachor (our values) gives a straight line curve, and thus a definite relationship between the atomic number and parachor has been established. From the graph the parachor of caesium = 150.

In the previous investigation (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 37) the authors have shown from the measured parachor of several potassium salts, that by modifying the Hammick and Andrew's equation for calculation of parachors of solutes in solution, the parachors of inorganic salts in solution could be accurately determined. In the present investigation by employing the same modified equation (*loc. cit.*) the authors have determined the parachors of some lithium, sodium and rubidium salts, and the atomic parachors of the above elements including caesium.

Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 43) has determined the parachors of some ammonium salts and of potassium chloride and iodide in aqueous solution, and finds the value of parachor in each case to be less than the $\Sigma[P]$ and is, therefore, of opinion that atomic parachor constants cannot be employed when the elements are in the ionic state. In the calculation of the parachor of salts above referred to, the parachor constant 52.62 for water has been used and the values for ammonium salts are found to be 10 units lower than $\Sigma[P]$. If 54 as the parachor constant of water (Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1188) is substituted in the calculation, the observed parachors of ammonium salts, however, closely approximate to $\Sigma[P]$.

In recent years anomalies have been found in the parachor constants of elements like palladium, thallium, mercury, iron, cobalt and nickel by Mann and Purdie (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1549), Anderson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1283) working on the metallic carbonyl compounds also

TABLE I.

Parachor of sodium salts.										
Subst.	<i>x</i> .	<i>D</i> .	<i>γ</i> .	<i>M_w</i> .	<i>P_w</i> .	<i>P_x</i> (Parachors observed by us).	<i>P_x</i> Parachor values obtained by Sugden (<i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1929, 1291) from Jaeger's data (<i>Z. anorg. Chem.</i> , 1917, 101, 1).	Atomic parachor of Na deduced from the <i>P</i> (obs.) of the salt by us.	Atomic parachor of Na obtained by Sug- den (loc. cit.) from the para- chors of the salt.	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
NaCl	0.09773	1.193	84.09	21.939	55.67	142.54	124.8	89.84	72.1	
NaBr	0.04190	1.166	78.30	21.561	55.01	156.06	143.8	93.46	77.4	
	0.04987	1.196	78.80	22.233	55.38	163.66	(mean 159.36).			
NaNO ₃	0.04972	1.123	74.27	20.731	54.20	58.92	152.9	91.1	61.4	
	0.05138	1.155	74.89	21.449	54.64	66.37				
	0.06109	1.173	75.90	22.093	55.56	79.53				
	0.07866	1.212	78.34	23.239	57.06	93.19				
							(182 from graph by extrapola- tion).			
Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	0.05230	1.301	86.80	25.324	59.42	315.0	Not done	84.9	—	
5H ₂ O	0.05451	1.312	86.91	25.634	59.65	315.2				
	0.05971	1.339	87.60	26.356	60.24	318.0				
							(mean 316.6)			
NaHSO ₃	0.04686	1.181	83.33	22.038	56.39	210.0	Not done	92.6	—	
at 35°	0.04882	1.190	83.95	22.203	56.49	209.8				
									(mean Na=90.06)	

observes anomalies in the parachor constants of nickel, cobalt and iron. No explanation has, however, been offered.

In the case of simple inorganic salts with definite linkages and composition it is reasonable to assume that the parachor constants, determined by the solution method, are free from any structural and packing influences and that the additive character of the parachor is maintained. A new and interesting relationship has been established for the alkaline group of elements between the parachor and atomic number in that the former is connected in a definite manner to the latter which is a fundamental property of the atom.

In Table I are given the data and results obtained with the solution in water of different sodium salts, at the constant temperature of 30°.

It will be noticed that (a) the parachor of the two salts—sodium thio-sulphate and sodium bisulphite—have not been previously determined on account of the difficulties of fusing them, (b) the parachor value of NaCl NaBr, and NaNO₃ obtained by the authors are distinctly higher than those obtained by others by the fusion method (*cf.* columns 7 and 8) and (c) that the mean atomic parachor of Na=90.06. In connection with the parachor of sodium chloride, the authors have also calculated this constant from the surface tension and density data of sodium chloride solutions obtained by Harkins and McLaughlin (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 2083), and the mean value calculated was 142.28 in close agreement with the value 142.54 found experimentally by solution method.

In the case of sodium nitrate when the salt is dissolved, there is a change in the volume directly proportional to the concentration, and consequently the parachor has been calculated according to the Hammick and Andrew's equation, and the final value deduced from a series of values of P_x by straight line extrapolation as shown in Fig. 1.

In calculating the P of sodium bisulphite the structures given below have been found to fit in with the measured parachor values.

Sodium thiosulphate
 $P_{\text{obs}} = 316.5$; $P_{\text{Na}} = 84.9$

Sodium bisulphite
 $P_{\text{obs}} = 20.9$; $P_{\text{Na}} = 92.6$

The observed parachor of sodium thio-sulphate is rather low, as it gives a lower atomic parachor of sodium than the other salts.

In Table II are given the data and the results obtained with two salts of lithium and one of rubidium in water at the constant temperature of 35°.

In this case also, the observed parachor values are higher than those obtained by fusion method. The mean parachor of Li equals 46·8 and of Rb 141·62.

Relation between Atomic Parachor and Atomic Number of the Metals of the First Group (Li, Na, K, Rb, Cs).

When the parachor constants of these metals as measured here are plotted against their atomic numbers, a smooth parabolic curve is obtained (Fig. 2 a). By plotting the logarithms of these two co-ordinates the straight line is obtained (Fig. 2b).

The logarithmic curve thus indicates that in the case of alkali metals, parachor is definitely connected with the fundamental property of the atom, namely, the atomic number or the nuclear charge.

The Atomic Parachor.

Parachor of Lithium.—Sugden ("Parachor and Valency," p. 181) has given the approximate value of parachor for lithium as 50 in error by ± 10 units. The mean value obtained by the authors is 46·8 and fits well on the straight line logarithmic curve discussed above. Consequently Sugden's figure may not be considered in error and may be regarded as correct comparing favourably with the value obtained by the solution method.

TABLE II.
Parachor of lithium and rubidium salts.

Substance.	α .	D.	Y.	M_M .	P_M .	P_A . (Parachor observed by us).	Parachor values obtained by Sugden & Wil- kins (J. Chem. Soc., 1929, 1291).	Atomic parachor of the metal deduced from the observed parachor of the salts.	Atomic parachor of the metal obtained by Sug- den & Wilkins (<i>loc. cit.</i>).
1									
LiCl	0·07650	1·006	77·11	5	6	7	8	9	10
LiBr	0·09095	1·354	83·68	19·873	53·7	100·34	97·2 to 99·6	Li = 47·64	45·7
RbCl (30°)	0·04282	1·197	78·32	24·26	54·2	112·36	Not done	Li = 45·96	—
				22·401	55·84	194·32	182·8	Rb = 141·62	Rb = (130) () = $\frac{1}{2}$ 10

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2a.

FIG. 2b.

Parachor of Sodium.—In the case of sodium metal Poindexter (*Phys. Rev.*, 1926, 27, 820) from the surface tension and density data of sodium metal, has arrived at the figure of 97.4 as the parachor constant; Sugden from the study of several salts by fusion method has arrived at the figure of 80 in error by ± 10 units ("Parachor and Valency," p. 181). The solution method gives the mean value of sodium parachor as 90.06. This appears to be more in line with the logarithmic "Parachor—Atomic number" Law, as established above and is in agreement with the higher expected value of Sugden.

Parachor of Rubidium.—The atomic parachor of rubidium is found to be 141.62 and this value fits exactly on the logarithmic curve Fig. 2 b.

Parachor of Cæsium.—From the study of fused salts of cæsium, Sugden has deduced 150 as the parachor of the metal atom. If the straight line Fig. 2 b is extended it also cuts the parachor co-ordinate at a point corresponding to 150. This, therefore, establishes the value of parachor of cæsium to be 150.

The results obtained by the "solution method" with the salts of alkaline earth metals and their parachor will be discussed in part III of the present series.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
D. J. SIND COLLEGE,
KARACHI.

Received April 26, 1938.
